

Magetan Regency MSME Strategy in The New Normal

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Abstract: This research aims to find problems that often hinder the development of MSMEs in Magetan Regency in the advantage of competing, especially in the face of The New Normal, for that there is a strategy needed in creating competitive advantages in The New Normal. The object of this research is small and medium enterprises in Magetan Regency. Data analysis techniques use descriptive analysis techniques. The results showed that competition between similar companies, the threat of new arrivals, the threat of replacement products, the bargaining power of buyers, and the bargaining power of suppliers are problems faced by small and medium enterprises in Magetan Regency.

Katakunci: Industry Rivalry, Threat of New Entrants, Threat of Substitutes, Bargaining Power of Suppliers, Bargaining Power of Buyers.

1. Introduction

In Indonesia, micro small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) have a very large role in national economic growth. The purpose of MSME Empowerment according to Law No. 20 of 2008 on MSMEs to realize a balanced, developed, and equitable national economic structure. Growing and developing the ability of MSMEs to be a resilient and independent business. Increasing the role of MSMEs in regional development, job creation, income equality, economic growth, and alleviation of people from poverty.

Based on Law No. 20 of 2008 article 1, Micro Enterprises are productive businesses owned by individuals and/or individual business entities that have micro business criteria as stipulated in the law. Small Business is a stand-alone productive economic enterprise, conducted by individuals or business entities that are not subsidiaries or non-subsidiary owned, controlled, or part of, directly or indirectly, from medium or large businesses that meet the criteria of small businesses as referred to in the law. Medium enterprises are stand-alone productive economic enterprises, conducted by individuals or business entities that are not subsidiaries or branches of companies owned, controlled, or parted either directly or indirectly with Small Or Large Businesses with the amount of net worth or annual sales results as referred to in the law (Tambunan, 2012).

In the current condition, many MSME actors in the service and production sector face various challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic, including a significant decrease in sales turnover, a decrease in the number of consumers who buy, difficulties in obtaining raw materials, and obstacles in product marketing (Rulandari, Rahmawati, & Nurbaiti, 2020)

Limitations are still owned by SMEs, such as product quality, capital limitations, marketing networks, and so on. It needs an environment conducive to SMEs, ensuring optimal collaboration with stakeholders in government, diverse business entities, and the world of education. Collaboration is directed to think strategically in creating a competitive advantage that is how to compete to be the best, compete to have uniqueness. SMEs should also focus on the integrity of their business units. All competitive advantages are in the value chain optimized through the implementation of an excellent value management supply chain. So SMEs can be directed to have superior performance through the application of operational principles of effective supply chain management and strategic positioning in their value chains to have a special competitive advantage to survive and even lead in this pandemic crisis (Fahriyah & Yoseph, 2020).

Some strategies that can be developed by MSMEs such as increasing product differentiation, cheaper prices from competitors, a good delivery system, and an easier payment system. The competitive climate that occurs in MSMEs tends to increase with the development of MSMEs in Magetan Regency, where the increase in competitors is accompanied by market demand that is also constantly increasing. alternative strategies that can be developed by MSMEs are to increase capital for business development, add production equipment machines, and training programs for employees (Foris & Mustamu, 2015).

Responding to the New Normal era, MSME actors focused on digital platforms as part of communication strategies by not abandoning traditional markets and mastering soft selling strategies. Through the implementation of marketing communication strategies, MSMEs can remain competitive and survive in the New Normal era (Rulandari, Rahmawati, & Nurbaiti, 2020).

Important factors and priorities that determine the performance of MSMEs are market availability, long-term efforts, quality control, business management, and sales promotion as internal factors and external factors, namely access to capital, access to market information, pro-business government policies, loan interest rates and technical guidance (Tajeri, 2020).

2. Research Method

This research uses descriptive qualitative to find out and get an in-depth interview of information related to the topic (Sugiyono, 2012). The subjects in this study were small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Magetan Regency as measured by 5 porter strengths. Data collection techniques through observation and semi-instructed interviews. Data validity test is done using triangulation test. Triangulation of sources conducted by researchers is interviewed to different MSME actors. In this research, the intended check is information obtained directly from researchers and will be compared with information directly from the MSME practice itself.

Identification based on Porter's Five Forces Model is described in their respective order by researchers because the model aims to facilitate researchers in grouping which models indicate opportunities so that they can be utilized as best as possible by the company and anticipate any threats that arise from the five models.

Figure 1. Porter's 5 Forces

3. Results and Discussion

Industry Rivalry

Competition between MSMEs is usually the biggest strength in five competitive forces. The strategy run by MSMEs can be successful if it provides a competitive advantage over strategies run by rival companies. Changes in strategy by one MSME may get a counterattack, such as lowering prices, improving quality, adding features, providing services, extending the warranty, and increasing advertising (David, 2006).

The intensity of competition among similar MSMEs tends to increase because the number of competitors is increasing. After all, competitors are increasingly uniform in terms of size and ability, and demand decreases, and because price cuts are increasingly common. The competition also increases when customers can switch brands easily when products are easily damaged, MSMEs different strategic terms, where they come from and culture, mergers, and acquisitions become common in the industry, as well as competition between similar MSMEs intensifies, profits decrease, in some cases even making an MSME becomes in very unattractive (David, 2006).

The feud between competing MSMEs tends to increase if the number of competitors increases because competing MSMEs become equal in size and ability, product demand decreases, and discounts become commonplace. The strategy run by one of MSMEs can succeed only to the extent that it provides a competitive advantage over strategies run by competitor MSMEs (David, 2011).

Threat of New Entrants

The threat of entry of new arrivals into the industry depends on the existing barriers of entry, combined with the reaction of existing competitors that the newcomer can predict (Porter, 1980). If these obstacles or obstacles are large and/or newcomers think there will be violent resistance from the old faces, then the threat of an influx of new arrivals will below.

There are six main sources of obstacles that come in, namely Porter (1987) namely: economic scale, product differentiation, capital needs, supplier switching costs, access to distribution channels, and unconstitutional costs regardless of the scale of Substitution product development. MSME actors in a competitive activity, in a broad sense with MSMEs that produce replacement products. Substitute products limit the potential profit of MSMEs by setting ceiling prices that can be given by MSMEs.

Threat of Substitutes

The more attractive the alternative price offered by replacement products, the tighter the profit restrictions. Recognizing substitution products (substitutes) is a matter of finding other products that can carry out the same functions as deep products made by MSMEs. The position in dealing with replacement products may be a collective action of MSMEs. Replacement products place an upper limit of the price that can be set before the consumer will be beautifying to the replacement product. The strength of competition from replacement products is best measured by the market share captured by the product, in addition to the MSME plan that increases capacity and market penetration (David, 2011).

Bargaining Power of Supplier

Bargaining power of suppliers can be a threat to MSMEs that have been getting input from suppliers in case of MSME dependence on one of the suppliers that become bigger over time. Indicators that can be used to see the dependence of MSMEs to one of the suppliers is a concentration ratio that can show the ratio between the amount of supply value from a particular supplier and the overall value of inventory supplied by various suppliers.

Suppliers can use the bargaining power of MSME practices by raising prices or lowering the quality of products or services purchased. Strong suppliers can therefore suppress the compulsion of MSMEs who are unable to offset the increase in their price (Porter, 1980).

Bargaining Power of Buyers

The bargaining power of consumers is also higher when what is purchased is a standard or uninformed product. When conditions are like this, consumers can often negotiate about selling prices, warranty coverage, and accessory packages to a higher level (David, 2006). Besides, the power of bargaining consumers is also greater if the products purchased are standard or no different. Competitor MSMEs may offer longer warranties or special services to gain customer loyalty if the bargaining power from consumers is extraordinary. Consumers can often negotiate selling prices, warranties, and packaging accessories to some degree (David, 2011).

4. Conclusion

The corona pandemic Covid-19 hit businesses, including the Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) sector. They have to face the reality of marketing decline due to the decrease in buyers who are piling up with the hit of people's purchasing power.

MSME actors must adapt to the current changes where consumer behavior switches from offline to online significantly as a result of the covid-19 pandemic. The government has urged people to do activities at home as a mitigation effort so that shopping center visitors fall by up to 50%. MSME actors must develop digital strategies as part of adaptation to be able to survive and also continue to develop in the current conditions.

Competition between similar MSMEs, the threat of new arrivals, the threat of replacement products, the power of bargaining buyers, and the bargaining power of suppliers are problems faced by MSMEs in Magetan Regency.

In overcoming increasingly tight competition among competitors, the strategy that can be done by MSMEs is to expand demand or strengthen the level of product differentiation by improving product quality and maintaining product quality. Do good marketing, and receive advice from customers without changing existing quality standards.

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